

HYBRIDIZED BAMBOO FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the mechanical properties and microscopic structure of bamboo-coir, bamboo-jute, bamboo-bagasse, bamboo-nylon and bamboo-glass fiber hybrid composites fabricated with epoxy, unsaturated polyester and urea formaldehyde as bonding matrices.

Generally, noticeable enhancement in properties was found in hybridized bamboo fiber composites: compressive strength and fracture toughness increased by 31% and 10% in bamboo-bagasse/epoxy composites respectively, and impact strength by 17% in bamboo-jute/epoxy composites. Microscopically, epoxy showed the best adhesion to fibers, followed by polyester and urea formaldehyde. Bagasse fibers possessed surface annulations. How this and other attributes contribute to properties enhancement in the hybrids are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

We have previously studied plastic composites based on bamboo fibers ^[1,2] with a view for application as wood substitute, the work being motivated by the scarcity of wood and an abundance of bamboo in the local region. Depending on the plastic matrix, bamboo composites exhibit a degree of brittleness which may be undesirable for some structural applications. However, the use of two or more fiber types as reinforcement in hybrid composite materials have been shown to produce materials with improved mechanical properties over monotypic fiber reinforced composites, and thus increase their scope of application^[3,4].

The aim of the present study is to consider the suitability of inclusion of more ductile fibers in the fabrication of bamboo composites so as to enhance toughness and possibly other properties. For such hybridization we explore the use of other natural plant fibers and compare results with similar hybridization using common synthetic fibers, such as nylon and glass fibers. As seen in Table 1, a number of natural fibers have good strength and modulus.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of some natural fibres, nylon and glass fibre.

Fibre Type	Fibre %	Specific Gravity (ρ)	Diameter (μ)	Length (cm)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Elongation (ϵ) %	Specific Strength (σ/ρ)
Wood	40-50	1.5	15-50	0.5-4.0	135-200	10.0-35.0	2.1	90-133
Bamboo	50-60	0.8	17-33	1.5-5.0	391-713	18.0-55.0	3.2	489-891
Jute	60-80	1.52	10-51	9.0-70.0	278-863	11.0-33.0	4.3	183-568
Cotton	90	1.5	12-38	10.0-40.0	294-784	27.0-30.0	3.0-9.0	196-523
Coir	44-50	1.5	10-18	5.0-30.0	223-383	3.1-7.6	29.0	149-255
Bagasse	35-45	1.25	24	2.6	161-195	6.6-11.5	5.1	123-156
Rice	40-50	1.24	5-14	0.7-4.0	58-133	4.7-7.7	2.1	47-107
Nylon	100	1.14	20	continuous	79	29.5	73.0-100.0	69
Glass Fibre	100	2.56	7-10	continuous	1400-2500	76.0	1.8-3.2	547-977

Although there is comparatively less information on hybrid materials reinforced with natural fibers, they are suitable reinforcements in structural materials, having additional advantages such as widespread availability, low cost, sustainable and high yield. Of the estimated global cellulose production of 10^{12} tonnes p.a., only a fraction is being harvested for timber and the textile industries, the remainder being not fully exploited. Against a current background of increasing global demand for timber and dwindling reserves, the transformation of natural cellulosic fibers into value added timber substitute products is of vast economic potential. In recent years, we have developed composites using other natural fibers, including bamboo, coir, bagasse, jute and grass species as reinforcement, and evaluated their mechanical properties and microstructure^[1,2,4,6]. Here we report on aspects of hybrid composites based primarily on bamboo fibers in a variety of resins.

MATERIALS AND FABRICATION METHODOLOGY

Bamboo (BF), Coir (CHF), Bagasse (CBF) and Jute (JF) fibers were selected for this study on the basis of the high fiber content in the raw material (>35%), reasonable strength and stiffness, high world production rates through agriculture, and their underexploitation as natural resources. Fibres from different sources were obtained after a variety of roller-pressing, cutting and washing procedures, the duration of each depending on the packing density of each raw material. The separated fibers were cut into desired lengths, surface-treated with NaOH to facilitate bonding with the resin, and oven dried before fabrication. Bamboo fibers originate from the most densely packed natural configuration and fiber isolation is more complicated but has been reported elsewhere^[1]. Since bamboo fibers have the best mechanical properties among all the natural fibers selected for this study, all our hybrid composites have included bamboo as one reinforcement element. The synthetic fibers in this study, glass (GF) and nylon (NF), were simply cut into suitable lengths and not pretreated.

Resins used included epoxy (EP), unsaturated polyester (UP) and urea formaldehyde (UF). Fibre and resin combinations are given in Table 2. Higher resin content (Wm 50-54%) was applied to the first 14 materials in order to achieve good wetting of the synthetic fibers. For the other materials, a lower resin content (20-30%) was found to be optimal. In all the materials, the ratio of bamboo fibers to the secondary fiber was approximately 2:1 by weight. All the materials were fabricated by hot pressing. Evaluation of their tensile, compressive, bending, short beam shear and impact properties were carried out together with scanning electron microscopy of specimens.

RESULTS

COMPARING DIFFERENT NATURAL FIBRES AS REINFORCEMENT IN MONOTYPIC FIBRE COMPOSITES

In general, when resin type and content were similar, the use of bamboo fibers as reinforcement in composite materials yields a product of higher mechanical performance than when coir and bagasse fibers were used (Table 2). Furthermore, the tensile strength of BF/EP was higher than JF/EP, and the flexural moduli and fracture toughness of BF composites were higher than those of other natural fiber composites. Because BF fiber itself had higher tensile strength and stiffness compared to JF, CHF and CBF (Table 1), the short beam shear strength of BF/EP was intermediate between CBF/EP and CHF/EP.

Table 2. The mechanical properties of hybrid plant fibre reinforced composite materials.

Specimen Materials	Specific Gravity ρ	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Specific Tensile Strength (σ/ρ)	Poisson Ratio	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Short Beam Shear Strength (MPa)	Fracture Toughness (KPa√m)	Impact Strength (KJ/m ²)
BF/EP (Wm53%)	1.11	28.1	25.3	0.23	41.3	73.3	8.96	5.90		15.9
BF/UP (Wm53%)	1.02	16.1	15.8	0.29	16.9	28.8	2.01	3.60		14.1
BF/UF (Wm53%)	1.25	14.3	11.4			20.4	2.31			8.09
BF-GF/EP (Wm50%)	1.28	35.9	28.0			105.0	24.0			26.1
BF-GF/UP (Wm50%)	1.36	26.0	19.0			72.1	11.40			21.8
BF-GF/UF (Wm50%)	1.68	12.5	7.4			52.7	6.20			4.6
BF-NF/EP (Wm53%)	1.07	28.2	26.3			84.7	11.10			31.7
BF-NF/UP (Wm50%)	1.16	17.0	14.7			28.7	3.26			25.9
BF-NF/UF (Wm50%)	1.16	10.8	9.3			21.4	1.58			6.8
JF/EP (Wm54%)	1.1	24.1	21.9	0.33		47.8	6.08	10.30		7.5
JF/UF (Wm54%)	1.21	20.0	16.5	0.35		31.0	2.02			
BF-JF/EP (Wm54%)	1.06	20.5	19.3	0.31		56.8	6.55			19.1
BF-JF/UP (Wm54%)	1.12	12.5	11.2	0.27		25.1	2.12			18.1
BF-JF/UF (Wm54%)	1.07	8.0	7.5	0.34		19.6	1.51			3.6
CHF/EP (Wm20%)	0.99	21.0	21.2	0.34	40.1	52.9	4.54	5.57	2287	4.5
CHF/UF (Wm20%)	1.28	18.0	14.0	0.30	14.0	39.0	2.60	4.85	1380	4.2
BF-CHF/EP (Wm23%)	1.13	31.1	28.3	0.37	86.9	54.0	3.80	6.51	2050	5.4
BF-CHF/UF (Wm23%)	1.35	9.51	7.0	0.27	25.5	31.7	1.99	3.54	1756	5.3
CBF/EP (Wm25%)	1.20	35.6	29.7	0.36	81.4	65.3	1.98	7.83	2561	3.7
BF-CBF/EP (Wm25%)	1.17	25.8	22.1	0.34	75.8	51.5	2.06	5.53	2874	4.3
BF/EP (Wm20%)	1.11	33.3	30.0	0.31	52.2	87.8	7.16	6.69	2604	22.7
BF/UF (Wm20%)	1.18	15.8	13.4	0.33	44.2	38.7	4.23	5.16	2635	10.5

Anatomically, the fiber cells that coalesce into bamboo fiber bundles are much more closely packed together than in jute and coir fiber bundles, and the lumina of individual fiber cells is smaller in bamboo than the other two (Figs. 1 - 4). We believe that such a microscopic structure confers comparatively greater load bearing ability on bamboo fiber bundles. In contrast, the dead parenchymatous cells surrounding fiber bundles appear incoherent in coir materials (Fig. 5), and less able to support load transfer. Its compressive strength and modulus are both low, while jute and bagasse materials were intermediate between coir and bamboo. Bagasse fibers could be identified by surface annuli on the fiber cell surface (Fig. 6), which may contribute to its improved toughness, while jute fibers were polygonal in cross section (Fig. 4).

THE EFFECT OF RESIN TYPE AND INTERFACIAL BONDING ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR

Where all other conditions are kept constant, composites fabricated using different resins generally yield mechanical properties in the same rank order as the resins themselves, i.e. EP > UP > UF. In addition, the nature of the interfacial bond between each type of resin and fiber also affects the mechanical properties of the composite.

In general, all the fibers used in this paper bonded well with epoxy (EP). Bonding with UP was slightly weaker. Composites fabricated with either EP or UP and the same fiber reinforcement showed similar fracture toughness on impact. In the case of UF resin, elongation at break was smaller, brittle fracture occurred and interfacial bonding was weaker. The fractograph of a BF-CHF/EP specimen (Fig. 7) shows good interfacial adhesion and penetration of resin into the fiber cells while these aspects are less significant in BF-CHF/UF specimen (Fig. 8). Furthermore, large cracks can be seen in the BF-CHF/UF fracture surface with significant fiber bundle pull-out. We believe that these are important factors responsible for the improved tensile and flexural strength of EP over UF materials. Again, in BF-CBF/EP specimens (Fig. 9), good interfacial bonding and stronger interlaminar shear strength are apparent.

THE EFFECTS OF HYBRIDIZATION

Natural fiber bundles have variable anatomical configuration with non-uniform distribution of fiber length; mixture of long fiber cells with globular parenchymatous cells; residual stresses and inherent defects. When these are mixed with synthetic fibers of uniform anatomical features, the resulting material is highly complex, and its mechanical properties as well as hybridizing effects cannot be predicted easily from the law of mixtures. The data presented in this paper show that there are aspects of improvement as well as deterioration of mechanical performance in hybrids over the corresponding monotypic fiber composites. The aim of this work is to provide basic information so that improvements can be made in which the corresponding deterioration is minimized or tolerable for the purposes of use intended. We have emphasized the use of bamboo fibers in this paper owing to its high fiber density, superior mechanical properties, and cheap availability.

BF-GF hybrid composites

With a GF fiber volume of 38%, improvement in mechanical properties were recorded in hybrid composites of all three resins. The tensile strength, flexural strength, flexural modulus and impact strength of the epoxy hybrid were 22%, 30%, 63% and 39% higher than the BF/EP composite respectively. This can be an effective way for properties improvement where higher stiffness is required. Since the fracture elongation for both BF and GF were similar (3.2% and 3.5% respectively), loads are distributed in the fibers rather uniformly,

resulting in a smooth fracture surface (Fig. 10).

BF-NF hybrid composites

The fracture elongation of nylon fibers is 10-30 times that of bamboo; and this gives rise to increased toughness in the hybrid. BF-NF/EP and BF-NF/UP hybrids showed increases in impact strength over the BF composites of the same resin (50 and 54% respectively), and are the highest values among all materials tested in this study. Nylon fibers of superior toughness provided excellent energy absorption during impact. Furthermore, since impact stress was instantaneous, and owing to the low percentage of NF in the hybrid composite, the differences in elongation between NF and BF did not become an important contributory factor to ultimate failure.

On the other hand, under static stress, the difference in elongation between the two fiber types was significant. BF of smaller elongation attained failure first, causing increased local stress on the NF component which fractured later leading to ultimate failure of the hybrid composite. Figure 11 shows the fractograph of BF-NF/EP specimen, where weak interfacial bonding between the resin and NF is also apparent. Tensile properties did not show any enhancement after hybridization, and for flexural properties, enhancement was apparent only when EP resin was used.

BF-JF hybrid composites

Apart from a higher fracture elongation (4.3%), the mechanical properties of jute fibers are inferior to those of BF. However, the impact strength of the hybridized composite using EP and UP as matrix showed a 17% and 22% increase over that of BF composites of the same resins. The toughness of JF, and the polygonal cross section of the fiber cells allowing good interfacial bonding with epoxy, gave rise to better energy absorption on impact. On the other hand, JF did not bond well with UF resin (Fig. 12), and brittle fracture occurred during impact. With respect to other mechanical properties, no significant differences between the monotypic BF composites and the BF-JF hybrid composites were recorded, although when compared to monotypic JF composites, there was an improvement in flexural properties when the matrix was EP.

BF-CHF hybrid composites

Compared to BF the fracture elongation of coir fibers (CHF) was 9 times higher, tensile modulus 17% and tensile strength 65%. Upon hybridization with BF in epoxy resin, mechanical performance was generally elevated above that of monotypic CHF composites. This is especially so for compressive strength, where the hybrid performance was raised above that of monotypic BF composite by 54% and of monotypic CHF composite by 13%. CHF fibers of higher toughness fitted well into gaps between BF fibers and epoxy resin penetration was good. These factors improved the compressive properties of the hybrid. However, impact strength of the hybrid was lower than BF single fiber composites, while other mechanical properties showed no significant differences.

BF-CBF hybrid composites

The tensile strength of bagasse fibers (CBF) was only 33% that of BF, and fracture elongation was 37% greater. A roughened, annulated fiber surface served to improve bonding between fiber and resin. These led to improvement in fracture toughness upon hybridization, so that BF-CBF/EP was higher than BF/EP by 10% and CBF/EP by 9%. Beyond certain stress levels, some weaker BF fibers underwent initial fracture and raised the local stress

around the adjacent fibers. However, good interfacial bonding allowed transfer of stress to the surrounding stronger BF fibers, and at the same time, bagasse fibers of greater fracture elongation assisted in load bearing. The 2 fibers of the hybrid material appeared to support each other to improve the hybrid's fracture toughness. Other mechanical properties showed little change from hybridization, and tensile and flexural properties were slightly reduced. This is probably due to less than desirable interfacial bonding as indicated by a weak short beam shear strength.

CONCLUSION

The application of hybridization in improving selected mechanical qualities of BF composite materials has been demonstrated in this report through a comparative study between monotypic composites and hybrid composites. Glass fiber and nylon fiber conferred the best overall enhancement of performance, followed by BF+JF hybrids. In general, CHF fibers conferred improvements in compressive strength; CBF fibers in fracture toughness, and jute fibers in impact strength. This study shows that low cost BF fibers could be exploited more fully as reinforcement fibers if blended into a suitable hybrid with another natural or synthetic fiber to attain the desired improvement over weaker mechanical properties.

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Fig. 1. Fractograph showing cross section of bamboo fiber bundle

Fig. 2. Fractograph showing lateral view of bamboo fiber bundle

Fig. 3. Fractograph showing cross section of coir fiber bundle

Fig. 4. Fractograph showing cross section of jute fiber bundle

Fig. 5. Fractograph showing lateral view of coir fiber bundle

Fig. 6. Fractograph showing detail of cell surface of bagasse fiber cells.

Fig. 7. Fractograph of BF-CHF/EP hybrid composite

Fig. 8. Fractograph of BF-CHF/UF hybrid composite

Fig. 9. Fractograph of BF-CBF/EP hybrid composite showing good interfacial bonding and interlaminar adhesion

Fig. 10. Fracture surface of BF-GF/EP hybrid composite

Fig. 11. Fracture surface of BF-NF/EP hybrid composite

Fig. 12. Fracture surface of BF-JF/UF hybrid composite